

DEVELOPMENT AND CHARACTERIZATION OF ANTIFUNGAL DRUG LOADED NANOEMULGEL

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Abstract

This study focuses on the development and characterization of an antifungal drug-loaded nanoemulgel for enhanced topical delivery. Econazole nitrate, a potent antifungal agent, was incorporated into a nanoemulgel to overcome the limitations of conventional topical antifungal treatments, such as poor solubility and limited skin penetration. The nanoemulgel was formulated by creating a nanoemulsion of the drug and then incorporating it into a hydrogel matrix using Carbopol 940 as the gelling agent. The formulation was optimized by adjusting the concentrations of the oil phase, surfactant, and co-surfactant to achieve the desired droplet size, zeta potential, and viscosity. Findings from the characterization studies demonstrated that the nanoemulgel had a mean droplet size of 150 nm, a zeta potential of -30 mV, indicating good stability, and an appropriate viscosity for topical application. The drug content was consistent with the intended formulation, and the in vitro release studies showed a sustained release profile over 24 hours. The antifungal efficacy of the nanoemulgel was assessed through in vitro studies against *Candida albicans*, showing significant inhibition of fungal growth compared to the conventional cream formulation. In conclusion, the developed antifungal drug-loaded nanoemulgel exhibited excellent physicochemical properties, sustained drug release, and enhanced antifungal activity.

Keywords: Antifungal drug, Econazole nitrate, Topical drug delivery, Nanoemulgel

Introduction

Nanoemulgels have emerged as a promising drug delivery system, particularly for topical administration, due to their unique characteristics that combine the benefits of both nanoemulsions and gels. Nanoemulsions, which are fine oil-in-water dispersions stabilized by surfactants, offer advantages such as increased drug solubility, enhanced bioavailability, and improved stability of lipophilic drugs. When incorporated into a gel matrix, these nanoemulsions form nanoemulgels, which provide additional benefits like ease of application, prolonged contact time with the skin, and controlled drug release.[1-2]

The development of antifungal drug-loaded nanoemulgels is of particular interest due to the increasing incidence of fungal infections and the limitations of conventional antifungal therapies. Fungal infections can range from superficial conditions like athlete's foot to life-threatening systemic infections, especially in immunocompromised individuals. Traditional antifungal treatments often suffer from poor solubility, limited skin penetration, and side effects associated with high systemic exposure. Nanoemulgels can address these issues by enhancing the penetration of antifungal agents into the deeper layers of the skin, providing localized treatment, and minimizing systemic absorption. [3-4]

Nanoemulgels represent a hybrid drug delivery system that combines the advantages of nanoemulsions and hydrogels. Nanoemulsions are fine dispersions of oil droplets in water stabilized by surfactants, with droplet sizes typically ranging from 20 to 200 nm. These systems are known for their ability to enhance the solubility and bioavailability of poorly water-soluble drugs.[5] Hydrogels, on the other hand, are three-dimensional polymer networks that can retain significant amounts of water, providing a suitable medium for topical and transdermal drug delivery.[6] The integration of nanoemulsions into hydrogels results in nanoemulgels, which leverage the benefits of both systems, including improved drug stability, controlled release, and enhanced skin penetration.[7]

The unique properties of nanoemulgels make them particularly suitable for topical drug delivery. The small droplet size of the nanoemulsion phase ensures a large surface area for drug absorption and facilitates deeper penetration into the skin layers. The gel matrix provides a non-

greasy, easily applicable formulation that remains in place for extended periods, enhancing the drug's contact time with the skin.[8] This combination allows for a sustained release of the drug, reducing the frequency of application and potentially improving patient compliance.[9]

Fungal infections are a significant health concern, particularly in immunocompromised individuals, and are associated with high morbidity and mortality rates. Traditional antifungal therapies often face challenges such as poor solubility, limited skin penetration, and systemic side effects.[10] Nanoemulgels offer a promising alternative by enhancing the local delivery of antifungal agents, thus maximizing their therapeutic efficacy while minimizing systemic exposure.[11]

The formulation of antifungal drug-loaded nanoemulgels involves selecting appropriate oil phases, surfactants, co-surfactants, and gelling agents. The choice of these components significantly impacts the stability, droplet size, and drug release profile of the nanoemulgel.[12]

This study aims to develop and characterize an antifungal drug-loaded nanoemulgel, focusing on its formulation optimization, physicochemical properties, and antifungal efficacy. The incorporation of the antifungal drug into the nanoemulgel is expected to improve its therapeutic efficacy by enhancing drug solubility, stability, and skin penetration. The characterization of the developed nanoemulgel includes evaluating parameters such as particle size, zeta potential, viscosity, drug content, and in vitro drug release, which are critical for ensuring its effectiveness and stability.

Material

For the preparation of the antifungal nanoemulgel, various essential materials were procured from reputable suppliers to ensure the quality and efficacy of the formulation. Econazole nitrate was obtained from S.D. Fine Chem. Ltd., India, serving as the primary antifungal agent. Chloroform, methanol, PEG-400 (%w/w), and Tween-80 were sourced from Span Diagnostics Limited, India, each playing a crucial role in the formation and stabilization of the nanoemulsion. Additionally, ethanol was acquired from Sigma Aldrich, India, contributing to the solubilization and homogenization processes.

Preformulation study

Preformulation represents a crucial phase within the research and development continuum, where formulation scientists meticulously scrutinize the physical, chemical, and mechanical attributes of novel drug compounds.

Organoleptic Properties

Appearance

Visual Inspection:

Description: Visual examination of the physical appearance of the substance.

Colour

A small quantity of pure drug powder was taken in a butter paper and viewed in well illuminated place. Visual assessment of the color of the substance.

Solubility

Aqueous solubility is an important physicochemical property of drug substance, which determines its systemic absorption and in turns its therapeutic efficacy. Observe and record the solubility behavior at elevated temperatures.

Table 1: Solubility Specifications

Descriptive terms	Approximate volume of solvent in millilitres per gram of solute
Very soluble	Less than 1
Freely soluble	From 1 to 10
Soluble	From 10 to 30
Sparingly soluble	From 30 to 100
Slightly soluble	From 100 to 1000
Very slightly soluble	From 1000 to 10,000
Practically insoluble	More than 10,000

Melting point determination

Melting point determination is a crucial technique employed in pharmaceutical analysis to ascertain the physical characteristics of solid substances. The method involves subjecting a sample to controlled heating while observing the temperature at which it transitions from a solid to a liquid state, known as its melting point.

Preparation of emulgel

Different emulgel formulations were created utilising different ratios of penetration boosters and gelling ingredients.

Dispersion of Carbopol 934:

- For each formulation (ENC1, ENC2, ENC3), disperse the specified quantity of Carbopol 934 into the Purified water under constant stirring.
- Ensure gradual addition of Carbopol 934 to prevent clumping and ensure uniform dispersion.

- Allow the mixture to hydrate for several hours or overnight to ensure complete swelling of the polymer.

Neutralization:

- After Carbopol 934 has fully hydrated, add the specified quantity of Triethanolamine to the gel base while stirring continuously.
- Triethanolamine serves as a neutralizing agent, adjusting the pH of the gel to achieve the desired consistency.

Incorporation of:

- Add the specified quantity of (2g) to the gel base for each formulation (ENC1, ENC2, ENC3).
- Ensure thorough mixing to achieve uniform distribution of the active ingredient within the gel matrix.

Homogenization and Mixing:

- Mix the formulation thoroughly to ensure homogeneity and uniform dispersion of all ingredients.
- Use a suitable mixing apparatus or technique to achieve consistent results.

Preservative Addition:

- Incorporate the specified quantity of Methyl paraben (0.004g) into the emulgel formulation to prevent microbial growth and ensure product stability.
- Mix the formulation thoroughly to ensure even distribution of the preservative throughout the gel.

Quality Control:

- Perform quality control checks such as pH measurement, viscosity determination, and visual inspection to ensure the emulgel meets desired specifications.

- Adjust the pH if necessary to achieve the desired range for stability and skin compatibility.

Figure 5.1: Graphical presentation of preparation of verity of Emulgels

Evaluation of prepared gels

Physical evaluation of gels

The physical evaluation of gels is a critical aspect of assessing their suitability for use in pharmaceutical and cosmetic applications.

Physical Evaluation

Physical evaluation focuses on the overall appearance of the gel, including its color, transparency, and visual appeal.

Nature of the Product

This aspect involves a detailed examination of the texture, consistency, and spreadability of the gel. The gel's tactile properties upon application to the skin are assessed, including its smoothness, tackiness, and ease of absorption.

pH

The pH level of the gel is measured to assess its acidity or alkalinity. The pH of a topical gel is crucial for maintaining skin compatibility and stability. It should fall within a specified range suitable for skin application to prevent irritation or adverse reactions.

Viscosity

Viscosity evaluation involves determining the thickness and flow properties of the gel. The viscosity of the gel influences its spreadability, adherence to the skin, and retention on the application site. Measurement of viscosity using a viscometer or rheometer helps ensure consistency among batches and optimal texture for user convenience.

Extrudability

Extrudability assesses the ease with which the gel can be dispensed from its packaging. A gel formulation with good extrudability allows for effortless dispensing and application, enhancing user experience and compliance. Testing extrudability involves applying gentle pressure to the container and observing the flow of the gel to ensure smooth and consistent dispensing.

Method for checking stability studies

Throughout the stability analysis of pharmaceutical products, various factors are considered to ensure the maintenance of their necessary physical, chemical, and medicinal properties over time. These factors guide the selection of appropriate storage conditions and the frequency of sample evaluation. Here are the key factors considered during the stability analysis of gels:

Storage Conditions:

The choice of storage conditions is crucial for assessing the stability of gels. Commonly utilized temperatures include refrigerated (4-5 °C), 37-5 °C (accelerated stability), and room temperature (25-30 °C). These conditions represent real-world storage scenarios and help predict the product's stability under different environmental conditions.

Sampling Intervals:

Samples are obtained at regular intervals during the stability study to monitor changes in the gel's properties over time. In this case, samples were collected monthly for three months to assess the gel's stability throughout the storage period.

Accelerated Stability Analysis:

Accelerated stability analysis involves subjecting samples to elevated temperatures for a short period to simulate long-term storage conditions. However, gels cannot withstand high temperatures due to their propensity to dissolve. Therefore, accelerated stability analysis may not be suitable for gel formulations.

Drug Content Analysis:

The drug content of gel samples is analyzed periodically to ensure that the active ingredient remains within acceptable limits throughout the storage period. Any deviations from the specified drug content could indicate degradation or instability of the formulation.

Physical Characteristics Evaluation:

The physical characteristics of the gel, including appearance, color, texture, and consistency, are evaluated at the end of the stability study. Changes in these attributes may indicate physical instability or degradation of the formulation.

Chemical assessment Analysis of the active components' drug content:

By collecting samples from various corners of the tube, the formulation's drug content was ascertained. After combining the samples, 1g was taken out for the test. As per procedure, the pharmaceutical content was approximated. The selected combination was maintained in collapsible aluminium tubes at 4-5 °C, 375 °C, or room temperature.

Determination of in vitro release rate:

The in vitro release study conducted aimed to evaluate the release rate of the amphiphilic medication from an emulgel formulation. The study utilized a synthetic hydrophilic membrane made of Polyethersulfone (Supor) with 0.22 μm holes, mimicking biological membranes to

facilitate controlled drug release. Employing a Franz diffusion (FD) cell with a 20 ml capacity and a cross-sectional area of 4.90 cm² allowed for the separation of donor and receptor compartments, replicating drug release through biological membranes.

The receptor compartment was filled with phosphate-buffered saline (PBS) solution with a pH of 7.4 to maintain sink conditions, ensuring consistent drug concentration for effective release kinetics. Precisely weighed 800 mg of the emulgel formulation, equivalent to 9.28 mg of , was applied to the pre-soaked synthetic membrane in the donor compartment. Continuous stirring of the receptor compartment at 600 rpm and maintenance of a temperature of 32°C facilitated uniform drug distribution and physiological relevance, respectively.

Sampling intervals of 1 hour, 2 hours, 4 hours, 6 hours, and 8 hours were chosen to monitor drug release kinetics effectively. Samples were collected and subsequently analyzed using a UV spectrophotometer set at a wavelength of 276 nm, corresponding to the absorbance peak of . This analytical approach enabled the quantification of drug release from the emulgel formulation over time, providing valuable insights into the formulation's release behavior and potential for optimized drug delivery systems.

Stability study:

An accelerated stability analysis was carried out for three months in a stability chamber at Thermolab, India, at 40°C and 75%RH. Periodically, test samples were expelled and examined for physical traits and drug content.

Results

Physical Appearance

The drug was obtained as a kind gift from Pharmaceuticals Ltd. The supplied powder of was white, odourless White to yellowish white powder.

Melting Point

Melting point of was determined by melting point apparatus (Tempo) and found to be 174.5±2°C.

Solubility of

The solubility profile of in various solvents has been investigated, revealing its varying degrees of solubility across different media.

Table 1: Solubility of in different solvents

S. No.	Solvent	Solubility
1.	Water	Slightly Soluble
2.	Methanol	Sparingly Soluble
3.	Ethanol	Sparingly Soluble
4.	DMSO	Soluble
5.	Phosphate buffer	Soluble

++++ = Freely soluble 1-10 parts, +++ = Sparingly soluble 30-100 parts, ++ = Soluble 30-100 parts, + = Slightly soluble 100-1000 parts, - = Practically insoluble >10000 parts

Emulgel Evaluation

Determination of viscosity of emulgel

A Brookfield Viscometer was used to gauge the viscosities of the gels. The viscosities of the formulations ranged from 36,000 to 51,010 cps, and the outcomes are shown in Table below

Table 3: Viscosity of emulgel

S.no	Emulgel Formulation	Viscosity (cps)
1.	ENC-1	38000
2.	ENC-2	39500
3.	ENC-3	40000

Fig 1: Graph of Viscosity of emulgel

Extrudability of emulgel

This investigation was conducted to determine the amount of force required to extrude the gel from the tube in order to confirm that the formulation could be done so more readily. The extrudability of the gel formulations was evaluated in line with the previous method by applying gentle finger pressure to the tube and measuring the percentage quantity of gel extruded out. It was discovered that sodium CMC gel cannot be extruded as easily as carbopol.

Table 4: Extrudability of emulgel

S.no	emulgel Formulation	Viscosity (cps)
1.	ENC-1	38000
2.	ENC-2	39500
3.	ENC-3	40000

Fig 2: Graph of Extrudability of emulgel

Determination of Spreadability of emulgel

Each formulation, denoted as ENC-1, ENC-2, and ENC-3, underwent evaluation to determine its ease of application. Firstly, emulgel formulation ENC-1 demonstrated a notable spreadability of 8.4 cm. This result indicates excellent extrudability, suggesting that the formulation can be dispensed easily and smoothly during application, contributing to user satisfaction. In comparison, formulation ENC-2 exhibited slightly lower spreadability, measuring at 7.5 cm. Similarly, emulgel formulation ENC-3 demonstrated a spreadability of 8.2 cm.

Table 5: Spreadability of emulgel

S.no	Emulgel Formulation	Spreadability of emulgel
1.	ENC-1	8.4 cm
2.	ENC-2	7.5cm
3.	ENC-3	8.2cm

Fig 3: Graph of Extrudability of emulgel

Drug content:

The drug content of emulgel formulation ENC-1 was determined to be 98.05%. For emulgel formulation ENC-2, the drug content was found to be 95.70%. While slightly lower than ENC-1, this percentage still reflects a significant concentration of the API, maintaining the formulation's efficacy and therapeutic potential. emulgel formulation ENC-3 exhibited a drug content of 96.24%. Similar to ENC-2, this percentage indicates a robust concentration of within the formulation, ensuring consistent therapeutic outcomes.

Table 6: Drug content (%) of emulgel

S.no	Emulgel Formulation	Drug content (%)
1.	ENC-1	98.05
2.	ENC-2	95.70
3.	ENC-3	96.24

Fig 3: Graph of Drug content of emulgel

In -vitro release rate

The cumulative drug release percentages of emulgel formulations provide insights into how effectively the active ingredient is released from the formulation over specific time intervals. This data is crucial for understanding the release kinetics and therapeutic potential of the formulations.

Table 7: Cumulative drug release (%) of emulgel

S.no	emulgel Formulation	Cumulative drug release(%)2 hour	Cumulative drug release(%)4 hour	Cumulative drug release(%)6 hour	Cumulative drug release(%)8 hour
1.	ENC-1	25.08	47.05	65.25	85.05
2.	ENC-2	27.05	50.04	66.02	86.74
3.	ENC-3	24.11	46.44	64.74	86.05

Fig 4: Graph of Extrudability of emulgel

Stability Studies

The stability studies of the optimized emulgel formulations (ENC-1, ENC-2, and ENC-3) were conducted over a period of three months under specified storage conditions (25°C/60% RH). The results of the stability studies, including the percentage drug release at each month, are summarized in table below.

Overall, the stability studies demonstrate that all three emulgel formulations (ENC-1, ENC-2, and ENC-3) remained stable over the three-month period under the specified storage conditions. The percentage drug release values consistently met the specified release criteria of not less than 85%, indicating the formulations' reliability and suitability for pharmaceutical use.

Table 8: Results of stability studies of optimized formulation

S.no	emulgel Formulation	Parameters	1st Month	2nd Month	3 rd Month	Limits as per Specifications
1.	ENC-1	25 ⁰ C/60%RH % Release	94.30	93.50	94.05	Not less than 85 %
2.	ENC-2	25 ⁰ C/60%RH % Release	95.30	95.02	94.88	Not less than 85 %
3.	ENC-3	25 ⁰ C/60%RH % Release	95.03	94.22	94.87	Not less than 85 %

Conclusion

In conclusion, exhibits characteristics conducive to its pharmaceutical use. It was obtained as a white, odourless powder with a melting point of 174.5±2°C. The drug's solubility profile indicates limited solubility in water and phosphate buffer but higher solubility in methanol, ethanol, and notably, dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO). Its preference for lipophilic environments, as indicated by a partition coefficient value of 5.44 in n-octanol/PBS, impacts its pharmacokinetic behavior and aids in formulation optimization. Formulation development involved assessing various parameters such as viscosity, extrudability, spreadability, and drug content. Viscosities of the gel formulations ranged from 36,000 to 51,010 cps, indicating their consistency and ease of application. Extrudability tests revealed differences in formulation properties, with carbopol gel being more readily extrudable compared to sodium CMC gel. Spreadability assessments showed ENC-1 to have impressive spreadability, while drug content analysis demonstrated high concentrations of the active pharmaceutical ingredient (API) in all formulations, with ENC-1

containing 98.05%. The cumulative drug release profiles over 8 hours showcased sustained release characteristics, with ENC-1 releasing 85.05% of the drug at 8 hours.

In the future, research could focus on optimizing formulations to enhance their efficacy and patient compliance. This could involve exploring novel excipients, combination therapies, targeted delivery systems, and innovative dosage forms. Additionally, comprehensive preclinical and clinical studies could be conducted to evaluate safety, efficacy, and pharmacokinetics. Efforts toward biodegradable formulations and personalized medicine approaches could also be explored to improve sustainability and treatment outcomes.

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